

Deliverable 2.2.2.2

DATA ON CLIMATE AND RENEWABLE ELECTRICITY TARGETS
(VERSION 1, FEBRUARY 2025)

28.02.2025

Data on climate and renewable electricity targets (Version 1, February 2025)

Aksornchan Chaianong¹ [<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3817-2062>], Puru Malhotra¹ [<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-2954-0988>], Ioannis Milioritsas¹ [<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-5193-0862>], Silvia Weko¹ [<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8180-7046>], Johan Lilliestam¹ [<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6913-5956>]

¹ Sustainability Transition Policy Group, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, <https://ror.org/00f7hpc57>, Lange Gasse 20, 90403, Nürnberg

Published by

Sustainability Transition Policy Group, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

Acknowledgements

The authors of this article have used various preparatory works from the NFDI4Energy to create this portrait, and references have been made where possible. Thanks to all those who are not named.

The authors would like to thank the German Federal Government, the German State Governments, and the Joint Science Conference (GWK) for their funding and support as part of the NFDI4Energy consortium. The work was funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) – 501865131 within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, www.nfdi.de).

License

This document is published under the [Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). This license allows users to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator.

The license allows for commercial use.

The data is published with CC BY-SA 4.0. **Please cite it as:**

Chaianong, A., Malhotra P., Milioritsas, I., Weko, S., and Lilliestam, J. (2025): Data on renewable electricity targets (Version 1, February 2025). Sustainability Transition Policy Group, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15476149.

Chaianong, A., Malhotra P., Milioritsas, I., Weko, S., and Lilliestam, J. (2025): Data on climate targets (Version 1, February 2025). Sustainability Transition Policy Group, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15476049.

Table of Contents

General Information	3
Summary	3
Deliverable within NFDI4Energy	3
Introduction.....	5
Method	6
Dataset	7
Target data	8
Climate targets.....	8
Renewable electricity targets	9
Remarks and Future Works	9
Remarks.....	9
Future works.....	10
References.....	10

General Information

Summary

With less than 25 years left before industrialized countries have committed to reaching net-zero emissions, understanding how full decarbonization can be achieved is more important than ever. Across the world, countries are progressing towards this goal, perhaps not yet fast enough, but there is nevertheless substantial progress. This means the technical and political context is evolving and creating new drivers and barriers for continued decarbonization. There is also much policy activity from which we can and should draw experiences for coming policies. Today, these aims are hindered by a lack of data: other than for techno-economic variables, energy policy and political data are scarce, and machine-readable data even more so. In NFDI4Energy, we address this problem.

In the present deliverable, we tackle the challenge of consistent target data in energy scenarios or energy or climate policy analyses. We develop time-series datasets on decarbonization targets, specifically climate (greenhouse gas emission (GHG) reduction) and renewable electricity targets for 27 European Union (EU) countries. We started with the EU countries because their target formats are mostly uniform, which helps us develop a data collection protocol to make them machine-readable and consistent. In addition, both datasets are designed to allow the addition of further countries, including the severely understudied regions outside the OECD and G20 world, especially low-income countries, in upcoming work within NFDI4Energy.

We manually gathered the data drawing on primary (e.g., national and European target policies or decisions; the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) from the NDC registry of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change) and secondary data sources (e.g., existing but not machine-readable datasets, published analyses) to ensure that the dataset is both correct and up to date with the latest target announcement and to ensure completeness to the extent possible. The final dataset holds data on two variables (climate and renewable electricity targets), with a target announcement year from 1997 to 2023 for climate targets and from 2001 to 2022 for renewable electricity targets.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

This deliverable is part of Measure 2.2 (Energy policy regulation, political preferences, and logics), with two main deliverables (see below).

- D2.2.1.1 Data on landscape and environmental regulations for energy production and infrastructure
- D2.2.2.1 Data on policy support
- D2.2.2.2 Data on climate and renewable electricity targets (this deliverable)

This deliverable is also related to Task Area 4, where we have developed metadata schema (Measure 4.3 Development of metadata standards for energy research data) and energy policy ontologies (Measure 4.5 Policy ontology; published in other and forthcoming deliverables) – see Figure 1. In addition, the data gathered here will be used to inform holistic energy modeling in Measure 2.4, especially by providing actual targets to define scenarios. Moreover, this work provides a data collection framework and template for energy infrastructure regulation, which can help energy modelers/researchers integrate socio-political aspects into the energy system modeling tool/policy analyses.

Related deliverables and measures in NFDI4Energy: D2.2.1.1, D2.2.2.1, Measure 2.4, 4.3, and 4.5.

Figure 1: Links between measures within Task Area 2 and other Task Areas.

Introduction

To achieve the temperature targets of the Paris Agreement, every economic sector must transition to net-zero greenhouse gas emissions. For the energy sector, where plenty of technical solutions exist to this problem, this means a transition to zero emissions as fast as conceivably possible. This is incredibly challenging, both because of the scale of the transition needed and the required speed.

Energy policy-driven research has been essential in supporting policies and driving the transition. For example, energy systems modeling has grown strongly over the last decades. It shows multiple paths for how the energy transition can be successful and how the future energy system can be designed. Across the world, countries have implemented energy and climate policies, to promote technological development, support the deployment of zero-carbon technologies, expand and adapt infrastructures, or reduce emissions. Many of these policies have been successful, but many others have failed to achieve their aims. For upcoming analyses in support of the transition, there is a rich empirical literature from which to draw experiences. However, a key bottleneck for both energy modeling and policy analysis is data availability: especially for social and political aspects, this data is missing, or it is not machine-readable or under the FAIR principles [1], [2], [3], which holds empirical analysis and societally relevant, empirically-based modeling back.

To address this gap and provide data resources to enable politically and societally more helpful and realistic analyses, we have developed time-series datasets of energy policies under NFDI4Energy Measure 2.2 (Energy policy regulation, political preferences, and logics). This includes renewable energy and electric vehicle support policies, decarbonization targets, and energy infrastructure regulation.

The present deliverable 2.2.2.1 (part 2/2) focuses on targets as one distinct type of climate policy goal. Here, we gather, structure, and publish two types of national decarbonization targets: climate and renewable electricity targets. This data is intended to, for example, support energy system modeling notably (by providing actual targets to define scenarios, etc.) or policy research (by providing a time series of targets as input variables for policy analysis); of course, the data is valid and useable by researchers in any discipline or type of research question.

One example of the decarbonization target use cases is to model future energy scenarios, such as normative (target-setting) scenarios [4], [5]. This is mainly to answer a question: “How can a target be reached?” [5]. However, it is highlighted that the normative scenarios typically do not evaluate socio-economic discontinuities. As a result, policymakers/energy modelers need to integrate interdisciplinary insights from social-political sciences, engineering, and economics [4], and our Measure 2.2 supports this aspect.

Focusing on energy policy research and use cases, an example could be ratcheting up climate ambitions and policy stringency, which is necessary to meet each country's Paris Agreement Goals. To address this, scholars have studied the concept of prioritization in the implementation of agenda-setting/political signaling that countries typically use to declare commitment [6], [7] and the hypothesis of policy sequencing, meaning that imperfect policies at an early stage can be conducive to allowing stringent policies later. It is relevant both within and across policy processes [8], [9], [10], [11]. However, the process behind and function of targets and policies are complex and affected by disparate factors like each country's economic situation, the development and outlook of the needed technologies, and national or international political aspects. So far, such analyses have been scarce because they are methodologically challenging, and consistent datasets of different climate and renewable targets over long periods have been missing. Our datasets are the first step in filling this gap and enabling further and deeper analyses than have been possible before.

Much of the data in our target datasets have been primarily published in a non-machine-readable format, such as in [12], [13] for climate and renewable electricity targets, respectively. Here, we provide machine-readable and FAIR time-series datasets of targets. This way, energy modelers and researchers can incorporate socio-political data into the energy modeling software and the empirical analyses to support the continued improvement and development of energy and climate policies.

Method

We manually gathered the data from different sources, mainly from [12], [14], [15] for climate targets and from the Renewables Global Status Report series of REN21 [13] for renewable electricity targets. For all variables, we drew both on primary (e.g., the original NDCs from the NDC registry of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change [12]) and secondary data sources (e.g., existing but not machine-readable datasets, published analyses, such as from REN21 [13]) to ensure that the dataset is both correct and up to date with the latest target announcement and to ensure completeness to the extent possible.

The data presented in this deliverable holds a time series for decarbonization targets for all 27 EU countries in a machine-readable format, with geographical resolution according to the ISO country code (Alpha-3 code) [16]. The final dataset holds data on two variables (climate and renewable electricity targets), with a target announcement year from 1997 to 2023 for climate targets and from 2001 to 2022 for renewable electricity targets.

In each target dataset, we focused only on country-based and economy-wide targets, excluding certain target types, such as sector-specific targets. We also only focused on targets that already decided, not just only unofficially announced. Moreover, we recorded the original targets in a raw dataset and developed a consistent dataset to enable comparison of targets across countries. Consequently, there are two distinct datasets for each target. Also, if the target year is provided as a range (such as country A aims to achieve 100% renewable electricity “between 2050 and 2060”), we recorded the latest year in a range as the target year. Some countries announced the targets with a range. The targets' lower (minimum) and upper limit (maximum) were reported in these cases.

Focusing on climate targets, we recorded GHG emission reduction targets compared to a base year. These targets can be either conditional or unconditional. Sectoral targets (such as those for Emission Trading System (ETS) sectors) and targets without a target and base year were ignored. As shown below, climate targets can be categorized into four main types (derived from [17] and our data collection process). The baseline and trajectory targets have a high level of transparency in target setting because they directly imply the emissions level in a target year. On the other hand, business-as-usual (BAU) and intensity targets are less transparent because they depend on different factors, such as economic development [17].

- Baseline target (emission reductions in percentage, compared to a base year, often 1990)
- Trajectory target (emission reductions in X MtCO_{2eq} or a similar unit, in a target year)
- BAU target (emission reductions compared to a BAU scenario without (additional) policy action)
- Intensity target (emission reductions in MtCO_{2eq}/GDP or MtCO_{2eq}/capita, compared to a base year or BAU scenario)

We recorded all target types in the raw dataset. For countries that have already announced net-zero or carbon neutrality or climate neutrality targets, we assume there will be 100 percent GHG emission reductions in a target year, compared to 1990. We are aware that carbon and climate neutrality, for example, are not identical terms and may differ strongly in reality [18]. In most cases, governments do not specify precisely what they mean, so for this purpose and for the time being, we see it as justified

to assume that all such targets de facto mean net-zero emissions; in cases where the government specifies precisely what they mean with a “neutrality” target, we use that definition in the data.

In the second step, we normalized all climate targets to the 1990 level as a base year for the consistent dataset. We used the 1990 GHG emissions from the Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR; version 2024 [19]). If the announcement has a minimum and a maximum target, we took an average for the consistent dataset.

For renewable electricity targets, we reported only renewable electricity generation targets (ignoring renewable energy consumption targets at this moment). Renewable electricity targets were reported in different formats, most commonly as either a percent share of electricity generation or in generation units (such as TWh), for all renewable or specific technologies. Similar to the climate targets, we recorded all target types in the raw dataset. Unlike the climate targets, all renewable electricity targets in the EU are already comparable because all of them are in percent share of electricity generation for all renewables. As a result, in the consistent dataset, we only report the average value (for reported targets in a range) without further calculations (both the minimum and maximum targets are in the raw dataset).

Dataset

In our dataset, each column’s description is summarized in Table 1. Our dataset is interoperable with other data sources and NFDI infrastructure. For instance, we followed the ISO country code and the energy policy ontologies that we are presently developing in NFDI4Energy Task Area 4.5.1 (Development of policy ontology), expected for final publication and integration in the Open Energy Ontology (OEO) platform in fall 2025.

Table 1 List of column entries.

Column name	Target	Description
ISO_code	Both	The ISO country code (Alpha-3 code)
Country	Both	The country name
Year_decision	Both	The decision year is the year when the responsible authority made the decision to enact the target.
Year_first_decision	Both	The first target decision year
Year_target	Both	The target year (when the country aims to achieve the target).
Year_base	Only climate targets	The base year to compare emission reductions
Target_minimum	Both (only raw datasets)	The minimum target value. The negative value refers to the reduction, while the positive value refers to the addition.
Target_maximum	Both (only raw datasets)	The maximum target value. The negative value refers to the reduction, while the positive value refers to the addition.
Target_consistent	Both (only for consistent datasets)	The consistent target value. If the announcement has a minimum and a maximum target, we take the average for the conversion to consistent base year data.
Target_unit	Both	The target unit (such as in the percent share of electricity generation, MtCO _{2eq} , etc.), depending on the target types

Conditionality	Only climate targets	The conditionality of the target (unconditional targets vs. targets conditional on some further event, such as the target setting of other countries)
Target_type	Both	The target type <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate targets are baseline, trajectory, business-as-usual, or intensity targets. - Renewable electricity targets are all generation targets (as we did not include the renewable energy consumption targets at this moment).
RE_technology	Only renewable electricity targets	The renewable electricity technologies included for each target
Miscellaneous	Both	The general remarks of the regulation (if any)
Source	Both	The source of each target

Target data

This section briefly summarizes our dataset's key takeaways and implications for decarbonization targets. In the present version, it holds only EU countries.

Climate targets

All EU countries have announced baseline, unconditional climate targets. Only Czechia announced trajectory targets in 2017 in addition to its baseline target. No BAU and intensity targets were reported in the EU. Most EU countries decided their first climate targets in 1997, while some countries (Malta and Cyprus) did not.¹ introduced climate targets later (see Figure 1).

Figure 2 The EU countries made the first (economy-wide) climate target announcement.

The ambition of climate targets increases over time, which is in sync with the rising ambition of EU targets. For instance, after 2018, most EU countries (except Czechia and Poland) have set ambitious long-term climate targets (either climate neutrality or net-zero targets, depending on the countries²) to achieve by 2050 or earlier, in the case of Finland as early as 2035. Three countries (France, Malta, and Portugal) have announced their long-term targets as carbon neutrality by 2050. All these ambitious

¹ Cyprus also had an earlier target but it was not an economy-wide target so we excluded it from the dataset.

² The Netherlands also set an ambitious target (95% GHG emissions reduction from 1990 level by 2050), but does not call it as either carbon neutrality, climate neutrality, or net-zero.

long-term targets require much faster progress than recent trends, signaling ambition and seeking to guide future actions.

Renewable electricity targets

Most EU countries have also set homogenous renewable electricity targets, mainly for generation targets for all renewable technologies. Most countries set their first renewable electricity targets in 2001 and 2004 (see Figure 2).

Figure 3 The EU countries made the first renewable electricity target announcement.

The EU countries' renewable electricity targets are set to be consistent with their renewable energy targets. The renewable targets set in 2001 are indicative but refer only to renewable electricity production (the Directive on electricity production from renewables). Then, the EU introduced the Renewable Energy Directive and its revision in 2009 and 2018. As a result, most of the renewable electricity targets introduced during these years were transpositions to the electricity sector, as a part of each country's renewable energy target, which are not binding. Still, only the renewable energy targets are binding. It is also important to note that the revised Renewable Energy Directive in 2018 has no national binding, only an EU-wide binding renewable energy target is available [20].

EU countries have also set more ambitious renewable electricity targets over time, and some countries aim to reach 100 percent renewables between 2040 and 2050. For instance, Denmark announced their 100 percent renewable target in 2011 to be achieved in 2050, followed by Sweden (2040)³, Spain (2050), and the Netherlands (2050). This also signals more decisive actions to transform the EU's power systems.

Remarks and Future Works

Remarks

Correctness and completeness of data

We have done everything we can to ensure the accuracy and completeness of our dataset, including multiple review rounds with several FAU STP group members. Yet, we cannot guarantee that all information is correct and complete. It is, to the best of our knowledge. Not all data points are readily available; although we cite them correctly, documents may hold incorrect data. In some cases, interpreting regulations is a non-trivial task, especially in different languages, and we do not always

³ For Swedish, in 2023, the renewable electricity target was changed from 100% renewable to 100% fossil-free electricity generation to accommodate nuclear power [21].

know each country's energy-political context and tradition. We refuse any liability for any errors or inaccuracies.

Source of data

This dataset came from desk research. The source columns include links or references to each row's specific policy/target documents. All source links in our dataset are live as of February 2025.

Future works

We plan to keep updating targets for EU countries. For instance, the European Commission recently announced the RepowerEU plan [20], which has implications for renewable electricity targets, as reported in their National Energy and Climate Plans [22]. We plan to tackle these updates in the next version of our dataset.

In addition, we plan to publish an extended target dataset (climate, renewable electricity generation, and renewable energy consumption for more countries globally, including the severely understudied regions outside the OECD and G20 world, especially low-income countries. With the coming updates to expand the dataset to other countries, the usefulness of the data will be further improved.

As we broaden the dataset, we anticipate challenges in normalizing targets across countries, particularly climate targets. This is because other countries set not only a baseline and trajectory but also BAU and intensity climate targets. To ensure comparability, we will, for instance, need to identify BAU emission levels and normalize all targets to a baseline compared to the 1990 level.

References

- [1] S. Pfenninger, J. DeCarolis, L. Hirth, S. Quoilin, and I. Staffell, "The importance of open data and software: Is energy research lagging behind?," *Energy Policy*, vol. 101, pp. 211–215, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2016.11.046.
- [2] A. Chaianong, F. M. Hoffart, N. Kerker, J. Lilliestam, and S. Weko, "Datasets and time series for energy policy research and modelling," Feb. 2024, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10656917.
- [3] M. Chang *et al.*, "Trends in tools and approaches for modelling the energy transition," *Applied Energy*, vol. 290, p. 116731, May 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.116731.
- [4] R. Hanna and R. Gross, "How do energy systems model and scenario studies explicitly represent socio-economic, political and technological disruption and discontinuity? Implications for policy and practitioners," *Energy Policy*, vol. 149, p. 111984, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111984.
- [5] L. Börjeson, M. Höjer, K.-H. Dreborg, T. Ekvall, and G. Finnveden, "Scenario types and techniques: Towards a user's guide," *Futures*, vol. 38, no. 7, pp. 723–739, Sep. 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.futures.2005.12.002.
- [6] J. Meckling and J. Nahm, "The politics of technology bans: Industrial policy competition and green goals for the auto industry," *Energy Policy*, vol. 126, pp. 470–479, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2018.11.031.
- [7] L. Ollier, M. Melliger, and J. Lilliestam, "Friends or Foes? Political Synergy or Competition between Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 23, Art. no. 23, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.3390/en13236339.
- [8] A. Leipprand, C. Flachsland, and M. Pahle, "Starting low, reaching high? Sequencing in EU climate and energy policies," *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, vol. 37, pp. 140–155, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.eist.2020.08.006.
- [9] M. Linsenmeier, A. Mohommad, and G. Schwerhoff, "Policy sequencing towards carbon pricing among the world's largest emitters," *Nat. Clim. Chang.*, vol. 12, no. 12, pp. 1107–1110, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41558-022-01538-8.
- [10] J. Meckling, T. Sterner, and G. Wagner, "Policy sequencing toward decarbonization," *Nat Energy*, vol. 2, no. 12, pp. 918–922, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1038/s41560-017-0025-8.

- [11] L. Nascimento *et al.*, “Comparing the Sequence of Climate Change Mitigation Targets and Policies in Major Emitting Economies,” *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice*, vol. 0, no. 0, pp. 1–18, 2023, doi: 10.1080/13876988.2023.2255151.
- [12] “Nationally Determined Contributions Registry | UNFCCC.” Accessed: Feb. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://unfccc.int/NDCREG>
- [13] REN21, “REN21 Renewables Global Status Report,” REN21. Accessed: Jul. 31, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ren21.net/reports/global-status-report/>
- [14] European Environment Agency, “Tracking progress towards Kyoto and 2020 targets in Europe.” Accessed: Feb. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/progress-towards-kyoto>
- [15] Climate Change Laws of the World, “Climate Change Laws of the World.” Accessed: Feb. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://climate-laws.org>
- [16] ISO, “Online Browsing Platform (OBP).” Accessed: Feb. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search>
- [17] A. Chaianong and P. Castro, “NDC Transparency Meta-study - FAU CRIS.” Accessed: Feb. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://digitalcollection.zhaw.ch/server/api/core/bitstreams/152a4ef7-44f0-440f-8fb2-a5cc52a5e485/content>
- [18] N. Brazzola, “Ready for take-off? Exploring synergies between carbon dioxide removal and the aviation sector,” Doctoral Thesis, ETH Zurich, 2024. doi: 10.3929/ethz-b-000719824.
- [19] EDGAR, *Global Greenhouse Gas Emissions*. LU: Publications Office, 2024. Accessed: Feb. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset_ghg2024
- [20] European Commission, “Renewable Energy Directive.” Accessed: Feb. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/renewable-energy-directive-targets-and-rules/renewable-energy-directive_en
- [21] Regeringskansliet, “Förslag om nya energipolitiska mål inför den kommande energipolitiska inriktningspropositionen,” Regeringskansliet. Accessed: Feb. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.regeringen.se/pressmeddelanden/2023/12/forslag-om-nya-energi-politiska-mal-infor-den-kommande-energi-politiska-inriktningspropositionen/>
- [22] EMBER, “Draft NECPs show EU just falling short of REPowerEU,” Ember. Accessed: Feb. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://ember-energy.org/latest-insights/draft-necps-show-eu-just-falling-short-of-repowereu>